

Human Related Negative Planetary Impacts Assigning Responsibilities

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Summary

To most, the economic aspects of development take priority over environment for, on the one hand, we consume more than we can extract from planetary resources, and on the other, because greed and profit are more important than either planet or people. Living unsustainably has become a way of life, whatever the negative impacts maybe on Planet and People. The Industrial Revolution no doubt paved the way to lifestyles that demanded increased production of goods and services, leading to increased consumption, and increased production of waste. The trend until by the 60s, many started realising that unsustainable lifestyles which depended mainly on the Planet's finite resources could no longer be maintained. Numerable reports and recommendations have appeared in the last two decades, with much emphasis on sustainability and sustainable production and consumption. Mechanisms have been suggested and some put in place to reverse the trend. However, it appears we have failed. Populations are growing even faster than previously, the demand for goods and services keep increasing, the demand for land and deforestation is on the increase, increased emissions has become a serious health hazard, global warming and sea level rise are resulting increased human migration, and perhaps wild fauna too in the near future. The list is long. And in the meantime, the exploitation of both people and environment by the financially and technologically powerful, in other words the business community, making the rich richer and the poor even poorer, at the expense of both the environment and sustainability.

Introduction

The importance of the relationship between sustainability and human-related planetary impacts, affecting both society and environment been extensively studied and discussed in recent years, and the debate on how to reconcile the two continues. And while we are still at the cross-roads, such relationship was recognised and understood even in ancient times.

For a better understanding of how development and progress have ignored the benefits of our social and natural environments, and why the sustainability element has also been relegated to the background in our quest for more goods and services for all, and obviously more profit for some, we need to briefly examine the road we have travelled so far, the indicators we have failed to take heed of, and especially the voices we have ignored.

The human race is challenged more than ever before to demonstrate our mastery - not over nature, but of ourselves. **Rachel Carson – Silent Spring (1962)**

Rachel Carson no doubt had a vision of how humanity had been and still was on the wrong track as regards mismanagement of the environment, and the consequences that humanity would eventually has to face. Most opposed to her theories and views were businesses and industries – too concerned about productivity and profit – and least interested in sustainability and the welfare of the environment and future generations of people that populate our planet.

Historical Perspective of Society, Environment and Sustainability

Early civilizations

At the beginning of human history, human populations of the planet were small and mainly nomadic hunter-gatherers. Their demands, mainly in terms of firewood (energy), specific fruits, roots, plant parts, mammals and birds (food), and water on environmental goods and services were small and may have altered the natural composition of plant and animal communities to some extent, but not significantly enough to cause any environmental degradation or sustainability imbalance.

At some stage, some 10,000 years ago, agriculture and agricultural communities emerged in various parts of the world. Nomadic tribes settled down in specific areas as agrarian communities and became largely dependant on their environment for land, energy, food and water. Societies outgrowing their local food supply or depleting critical resources either moved on or faced collapse.

Later, intensified agriculture and increase in community sizes resulted in population increase and increased demands on environmental services. In some cases that led to deforestation resulting in flooding and soil erosion. Over-irrigation raised soil salinity decreasing land fertility and productivity. Eventually, decreasing agricultural production and other factors led to the decline of some civilizations. Some civilizations thought to have eventually disappeared because of poor management of resources include the Mayas and the Easter Islanders

However, stable communities adopting better farming practices and natural resource managements existed in some parts of the world, and large agrarian communities in China and India and elsewhere have farmed in the same localities for centuries.

Industrial societies

Technological advances over the years gave human communities increasing control and dependency over the environment. The industrial revolution of the Western world in the 17th to 19th centuries tapped heavily into the potentials of fossil fuels as sources of energy.

First coal and later oil were exploited to power ever more efficient engines and generate electricity. Their by-products found many other industrial and domestic applications. Their potentials for polluting the planet was either little understood or totally disregarded. Improved sanitation systems and advances in medicine protected large populations from diseases leading to increased human populations. The global population doubled from around 500 million to 1 billion people within a century (1650 to 1850).

Rapid and perhaps uncontrolled industrial, technological and scientific growth, marking the commencement of a period of global human influence known as the Anthropocene, has continued to this day.

Some (environmentally concerned) political economists began to express concerns about the environmental and social impacts of industry on society and human well-being. Others expressed the same fears and concerns through the Romantic movement of the 1800s. Overpopulation was discussed by Thomas Malthus, while John Stuart Mill (Schumacker, 1973) foresaw the desirability of a "**stationary state**" economy, thus paving the way for the modern discipline of ecological economics

Early 20th century

By the 20th century, the industrial revolution had led to an exponential increase in the human consumption of resources. The increase in population, health, and wealth of the West was perceived as a simple and natural path of progress. However, as early as the 1930s some economists began developing models of non-renewable resource management (Hotelling's Rule), and in the late 1970's about the sustainability of welfare in an economy that heavily uses non-renewable resources (Harwick's Rule).

By that time, ecology had gained general acceptance as a scientific discipline, and many concepts vital to sustainability were being explored. These included:

1. The interconnectedness of all living systems in a single living planetary system – the biosphere;
2. The importance of natural cycles (of water, nutrients and other chemicals, materials, waste); and
3. The passage of energy through trophic levels of living systems.

The rise of environmentalism

Following the deprivations of the great depression and World War II, the developed world entered a new period of escalating growth, a post-1950s "*great acceleration ... a surge in the human enterprise that has emphatically stamped humanity as a global geophysical force*".

However, a new environmental thrust pointed out that there were environmental costs associated with the many material benefits that were being enjoyed. Innovations in technology (including plastics, synthetic chemicals, nuclear energy) and the increasing use of fossil fuels, were transforming society. Modern industrial agriculture—the "**Green Revolution**"—was based on the development of synthetic fertilizers, herbicides and pesticides, which had devastating consequences for rural wildlife, as argued by environmentalist Rachel Carson in *Silent Spring* (1962).

In the 1970s environmentalism's concern with pollution, the population explosion, consumerism and the depletion of finite resources found expression in *Small Is Beautiful*, by British economist E. F. Schumacher in 1973, and the *Limits to Growth* by the Club of Rome, in 1975.

Late 20th century

Environmental problems started becoming global in scale, and the 1973 and 1979 energy crises demonstrated the extent to which the global community had become dependent on a non-renewable resource.

While the developed world was considering the problems of unchecked development, the developing countries, faced with continued poverty and deprivation, regarded development as essential to raise the living standards of their people.

In 1980 the International Union for Conservation of Nature published its influential *World Conservation Strategy*, followed in 1982 by the *World Charter for Nature*, which drew attention to the decline of the world's ecosystems.

In 1987 the United Nation's World Commission on Environment and Development (the Brundtland Commission), in its report *Our Common Future* suggested that development was

acceptable, but it must be sustainable development that would meet the needs of the poor while not increasing environmental problems.

Humanity's demand from the planet's natural resources has more than doubled over the past 45 years as a result of population growth and increasing individual consumption. In 1961 almost all countries in the world had more than enough capacity to meet their own demand; by 2005 the situation had changed radically with many countries able to meet their needs only by importing resources from other nations.

A move toward sustainable living by increasing public awareness and adoption of recycling, and the concept of renewable energies emerged. The development of renewable sources of energy in the 1970s and 80's, primarily in wind turbines and photovoltaics and increased use of hydroelectricity, presented some of the first sustainable alternatives to fossil fuel and nuclear energy generation, the first large-scale solar and wind power plants appearing during the 1980s and 90's

21st century: Global awareness

Through the work of climate scientists in the IPCC, there is increasing global awareness of the threat posed by the human-induced enhanced greenhouse effect, produced largely by forest clearing and the burning of fossil fuels. In March 2009, the Copenhagen Climate Council, an international team of leading climate scientists, issued a strongly worded statement:

The climate system is already moving beyond the patterns of natural variability within which our society and economy have developed and thrived. These parameters include global mean surface temperature, sea-level rise, ocean and ice sheet dynamics, ocean acidification, and extreme climatic events. There is a significant risk that many of the trends will accelerate, leading to an increasing risk of abrupt or irreversible climatic shifts.

Ecological Economics now seeks to bridge the gap between ecology and traditional, classical economics – it provides an inclusive and ethical economic model for society. A plethora of new concepts to help implement and measure environmental degradation and sustainability are becoming more widely accepted.

Global environmental human impact

According to the 2008 Revision of the official United Nations population estimates and projections, the world population is projected to reach 7 billion early in 2012, up from the current 6.9 billion (May 2009), and to exceed 9 billion people by 2050. Most of the increase will be in developing countries, whose population is projected to rise from 5.6 billion in 2009 to 7.9 billion in 2050.

Emerging economies like those of China and India aspire to the living standards of the Western world, as does the non-industrialized world in general. It is the combination of population increase in the developing world and unsustainable consumption levels in the developed world that poses a stark challenge to environmental degradation and sustainability

The Millennium Ecosystem Assessment concludes that human activity is having a significant and escalating impact on the biodiversity of world ecosystems, reducing both their resilience and biocapacity. The report refers to natural systems as humanity's "**life-support system,**" providing essential "**ecosystem services.**"

Healthy ecosystems provide vital goods and services to humans and other organisms. Two major ways to reduce negative human impacts and enhancing ecosystem services have been proposed (Daly, 1990):

1. Environmental management, and
2. Management of human consumption of resources.

Daly further suggested three broad criteria for ecological sustainability:

1. Renewable resources should provide a sustainable yield (the rate of harvest should not exceed the rate of regeneration);
2. Equivalent development of renewable substitutes for non-renewable resources; and
3. Waste generation should not exceed the assimilative capacity of the environment.

At the global scale, and in the broadest sense environmental management involves the oceans, freshwater systems, land and atmosphere, but following the sustainability principle of scale, it can be equally applied to any ecosystem from a tropical rainforest to a home garden, or from a large industrial estate to a small business.

Managing the Environment

Atmosphere

In March 2009, at a meeting of the Copenhagen Climate Council, 2,500 climate experts from 80 countries issued a keynote statement that there is now "**no excuse**" for failing to act on global warming and that without strong carbon reduction targets "**abrupt or irreversible**" shifts in climate may occur that will be very difficult for contemporary societies to cope with. Climate change, and its consequences, is now recognised as the worst situation this world has ever had to face.

Management of the global atmosphere now involves assessment of all aspects of the carbon cycle to identify opportunities to address human-induced climate change, and this has become a major focus of scientific research because of the potential catastrophic effects on biodiversity and human communities.

Other human impacts on the atmosphere include the air pollution in cities, the pollutants including toxic chemicals like nitrogen oxides, sulphur oxides, volatile organic compounds (**VOC's**), and particulate matter that produce photochemical smog and acid rain, and the chlorofluorocarbons (**CFC's**) that degrade the ozone layer. **Anthropogenic** particulates such as sulphate aerosols in the atmosphere reduce the direct irradiance and reflectance (**Albedo**) of the Earth's surface

Oceans

Ocean circulation patterns have a strong influence on climate and weather and, in turn, the food supply of both humans and other organisms. Scientists have warned of the possibility, under the influence of climate change, of a sudden alteration in circulation patterns of ocean currents that could drastically alter the climate in some regions of the globe.

Major human environmental impacts occur in the more habitable regions of the ocean fringes –estuaries, coastlines, bays, and small islands being more at risk. Trends of concern that require management include:

- Inland pollution and pollutants reaching the sea – including direct discharges
- Over-fishing (beyond sustainable levels);
- Coral bleaching due to ocean warming;

- Ocean acidification due to increasing levels of dissolved carbon dioxide; and
- Sea level rise and beach erosion due to climate change.

Freshwater

Awareness of the global importance of preserving water for ecosystem services has only recently emerged as more than half the world's wetlands have been lost along with their valuable environmental services. Biodiversity-rich freshwater ecosystems are currently declining faster than marine or land ecosystems, making them the world's most vulnerable habitats. Increasing urbanisation pollutes clean water supplies and much of the world still does not have access to clean, safe water.

Water scarcity, caused by such factors as population growth, increased farming and irrigation, deforestation, wastage, global warming, changes in rain patterns, desertification, has become one of the worst problems humanity is facing. The problem is more accentuated in developing countries.

Land

Loss of biodiversity stems largely from the habitat loss and fragmentation produced by the human appropriation of land for development, forestry and agriculture, as natural capital is progressively converted to man-made capital.

Land use change is fundamental to the operations of the biosphere because alterations in the relative proportions of land dedicated to urbanisation, agriculture, forest, woodland, grassland and pasture have a marked effect on the global water, carbon and nitrogen biogeochemical cycles, and this can impact negatively on both natural and human systems.

Forests

Present-day forests occupy about a quarter of the world's ice-free land with about half of these occurring in the tropics, but deforestation in the tropics is of major concern

Forest covers moderate the local climate and the global water cycle through light reflectance (Albedo) and evapotranspiration. They also conserve biodiversity, protect water systems and water quality, preserve soil and soil quality, provide fuel and pharmaceuticals, and numerous other ecosystem services and goods.

The United Nations Food and Agricultural Organisation (FAO) estimates that about 90% of the carbon stored in land vegetation is locked up in trees, and that they sequester about 50% more carbon than is present in the atmosphere.

Changes in land use currently contribute about 20% of total global carbon emissions.

Cultivated land

Feeding more than six billion human bodies takes a heavy toll on the Earth's resources. This begins with the appropriation of about 38% of the Earth's land surface and about 20% of its net primary productivity. Added to this are the resource-hungry activities of industrial agribusiness – everything from the crops' needs for irrigation water, synthetic fertilisers and pesticides to the resource costs of food packaging, transport and retail.

Food is essential to life. But the list of environmental costs of food production is long and not exhaustive:

- Topsoil depletion;
- Erosion and conversion to desert from constant tillage of annual crops; overgrazing;
- Salinisation;
- Solidification;
- Waterlogging;
- High levels of fossil fuel use;
- Reliance on inorganic fertilisers and synthetic organic pesticides;
- Reductions in genetic diversity by the intensive practice of monocultures;
- Water resource depletion;
- Pollution of water bodies by run-off and groundwater contamination;
- Social problems including the decline of family farms and weakening of rural communities

All of these environmental problems associated with industrial agriculture and agribusiness are now being addressed through such movements as sustainable agriculture, organic farming, and more sustainable business practices.

Extinctions and Biological Invasions

Although biodiversity loss can be monitored simply as loss of species, effective conservation demands the protection of species within their natural habitats and ecosystems. Following human migration and population growth, species extinctions have progressively increased to a rate unprecedented. Some scientific estimates indicate that up to half of presently existing species may become extinct by 2100. Current extinction rates are 100 to 1000 times their pre-human levels with more than 10% birds and mammals, about 8% of plants, 5% of fish and more than 20% of freshwater species threatened.

The greatest threat to biodiversity, after climate change, has become the destructive effect of invasive species. Increasingly efficient global transport has facilitated the spread of organisms across the planet. The potential danger of this aspect of globalisation is starkly illustrated through the spread of human diseases like HIV/AIDS, mad cow disease, bird flu, swine flu and others, but invasive plants and animals are also having a devastating impact on native biodiversity.

Management of Human Consumption and Sustainability

The underlying driver of direct human impacts on the environment is human consumption in terms of food, energy, and water. This impact is reduced by not only consuming less, but by also making the full cycle of production, use, and disposal more sustainable.

The ideas of embodied resource use (the total resources needed to produce a product or service), resource intensity (the resources needed for each monetary unit spent on a good or service), and resource productivity (the amount of good or service produced for a given input of resource) are important tools for understanding the impacts of consumption, with simple key resource categories indicating human needs being food, energy, materials and water.

Materials

As global population and affluence increases, so does the use of materials, which has increased in volume, diversity and distance transported. Included here are raw materials,

minerals, synthetic chemicals (including hazardous substances), manufactured products, food, living organisms, and waste.

Dematerialisation

This incurs converting the linear path of materials (extraction, use, disposal in landfill) to a circular material flow that reuses materials as much as possible, much like the cycling and reuse of waste in nature. This approach is supported by product stewardship and the increasing use of material flow analysis at all levels, especially in individual countries and the global economy.

Toxic substances

Synthetic chemical production has escalated following the stimulus it received during the Second World War. Chemical production includes everything from herbicides, pesticides and fertilizers to domestic chemicals, and hazardous substances. Chemicals of particular concern include: heavy metals, nuclear wastes, chlorofluorocarbons, persistent organic pollutants, and all harmful chemicals capable of bioaccumulation.

There needs to be rigorous testing of new chemicals in all countries, for adverse environmental and health effects. International legislations have been established to deal with the global distribution and management of dangerous goods.

Waste

Every economic activity produces material that can be classified as waste. The average human uses 45-85 tonnes of materials each year. To reduce waste industry, business and government are now mimicking nature by turning the waste produced by industrial metabolism into resources. Dematerialization is being encouraged through the ideas of industrial ecology, ecodesign, and ecolabelling. In addition to the well established “**reduce, reuse and recycle**,” consumers are more and more using their purchasing power for ethical consumerism.

Economic Dimensions of Environmental Sustainability

Sustainability economics represents:

... a broad interpretation of ecological economics where environmental and ecological variables and issues are basic but part of a multidimensional perspective. Social, cultural, health-related and monetary/financial aspects have to be integrated into the analysis.

Soederbaum (2008).

At present the average per capita consumption of people in the developing world is sustainable, but population numbers are increasing and individuals are aspiring to high consumption Western lifestyles. The developed world population is only increasing slightly, but consumption levels are already unsustainable and waste production uncontrolled.

The challenge for sustainability is to curb and manage Western consumption while raising the standard of living of the developing world without increasing its resource use and environmental impact. This must be done by using strategies and technologies that break the link between, on the one hand, economic growth, and on the other, environmental damage and resource depletion.

In addressing this issue, several key areas have been targeted for economic analysis and reform, including:

- The environmental effects of unconstrained economic growth;
- The consequences of nature being treated as an economic externality; and
- The possibility of a more ethical economics that takes greater account of the social and environmental consequences of market behaviour.

Decoupling Environmental Degradation and Economic Growth

In the second half of the 20th century world population doubled, food production tripled, energy use quadrupled, and overall economic activity quintupled. Historically, there has been a close correlation between economic growth and environmental degradation; as communities grow, so the environment declines.

There is concern that, unless resource use is checked, modern global civilization will follow the path of ancient civilizations that collapsed through overexploitation of their resource base. While conventional economics is concerned largely with economic growth and the efficient allocation of resources, ecological economics has the explicit goal of sustainable scales (rather than continual growth), fair distribution, and efficient allocation, in that order.

Sustainability studies analyse ways to reduce (decouple) the amount of resource (e.g. water, energy, or materials) needed for the production, consumption and disposal of a unit of good or service, whether this be achieved from improved economic management, product design, or new technology, or all of these. Ecological economics includes the study of societal metabolism, the throughput of resources that enter and exit the economic system in relation to environmental quality.

Nature as an economic externality

The economic importance of nature is indicated by the use of the expression *ecosystem services* to highlight the market relevance of an increasingly scarce natural resource that can no longer be regarded as both unlimited and free.

Part of the business of protecting the biological world has been the "**internalisation**" of these "**externalities**" using market strategies like ecotaxes and incentives, tradable permits for carbon, water and nitrogen use etc., and an increasing willingness to accept payment for ecosystem services.

Economic opportunity

Treating the environment as an externality may generate short-term profit at the expense of sustainability. Sustainable business practices, on the other hand, integrate ecological concerns with social and economic ones. Growth that depletes ecosystem services is sometimes termed "uneconomic growth" as it leads to a decline in the quality of life

The relationship between human rights and human development, corporate power and environmental justice, global poverty and citizen action, suggest that responsible global citizenship is an inescapable element of what may at first glance seem to be simply matters of personal consumer and moral choice.

Peace, Security, Social Justice

Social disruptions like war, crime and corruption divert resources from areas of greatest human need; they damage the capacity of societies to plan for the future, and generally threaten human well-being and the environment.

Depletion of natural resources, including fresh water, increases the likelihood of “resource wars” in some parts of the world. This aspect of sustainability has been referred to as environmental security and creates a clear need for global environmental agreements to manage resources such as aquifers and rivers which span political boundaries, and to protect global systems including oceans and the atmosphere.

Human relationship to nature

According to Murray Bookchin, the idea that humans must dominate nature is common in hierarchical societies. Bookchin contends that capitalism and market relationships, if unchecked, have the capacity to reduce the planet to a mere resource to be exploited. Nature is thus treated as a commodity:

The plundering of the human spirit by the market place is paralleled by the plundering of the earth by capital. **Bookchin (2004).**

Founded by Bookchin, “**Social Ecology**” is based on the conviction that nearly all of humanity's present ecological problems originate in, and indeed are mere symptoms of dysfunctional social arrangements. Whereas most authors proceed as if our ecological problems can be fixed by implementing recommendations which stem from physical, biological, economic etc. studies, Bookchin's claim is that these problems can only be resolved by understanding the underlying social processes, and intervening in those processes by applying the concepts and methods of the social sciences.

Deep ecology

Devall and Sessions (1985) established principles for the well-being of all life on Earth and the richness and diversity of life forms. This can only be compatible with a substantial decrease of the human population and the end of human interference with the nonhuman world. To achieve this, deep ecologists advocate policies for basic economic, technological, and ideological structures that will improve the *quality of life* rather than the *standard of living*. Those who subscribe to these principles are obliged to make the necessary change happen.

What the Future Holds

US President Obama's Promise (2008):

Generations from now, we will be able to look back and tell our children that this was the moment when the rise of the oceans began to slow and our planet began to heal.

Some two decades later the situation has hardly changed. But what one President promises may be overturned by another President, bringing out a serious question: **Should we leave the future of People and Planet in the hands of politicians?**

The earth has a finite capacity to provide resources and to absorb waste, but human demands already exceed that capacity. Current lifestyles in the developed world, to which many people in the developing world also aspire, rely on depleting natural capital and are unsustainable. The United Nations have stated in the Millennium Declaration: "*current unsustainable patterns of production and consumption must be changed.*" Yet the weight of information and

scientific evidence is often insufficient to alone produce necessary social changes, especially if these changes entail moving people out of their comfort zones.

But the transition required to reduce global human consumption to within sustainable limits involves much larger changes, at all levels and contexts of society. The United Nations have recognised the central role of education, and have declared a Decade of Education for Sustainable Development–2005-2014–which aims to "*challenge us all to adopt new behaviours and practices to secure our future*". The Worldwide Fund for Nature proposes a strategy for sustainability that goes beyond education to tackle underlying individualistic and materialistic societal values head-on and strengthen people's connections with the natural world.

A quick look at some of the fears expressed about our world would give us more food for thought and more impetus for reactions.

Earth Charter (2000) proposes that:

We must join together to bring forth a sustainable global society founded on respect for nature, universal human rights, economic justice, and a culture of peace. Towards this end, it is imperative that we, the peoples of Earth, declare our responsibility to one another, to the greater community of life, and to future generations.

The Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (2000) reveals the following:

- **Freshwater:**
 - *Water withdrawals from rivers and lakes for irrigation, household and industrial use doubled in the last 40 years.*
- **Pollution:**
 - *As the use of synthetic fertilizers has grown, humans have doubled the amount of nitrogen in the environment. Nitrogen in our air and water cause asthma and respiratory disease, blue-baby syndrome, cancer, and other chronic diseases.*
- **Climate:**
 - *Human-induced climate change is expected to raise the planet's mean surface temperature by two and a half to 10 degrees Fahrenheit, and sea levels will rise between three and a half to 35 inches in the next century.*
- **Fisheries:**
 - *At least 25% of marine fish stocks are overexploited or significantly depleted. In many sea areas, the total weight of fish available to be caught has declined by 90 percent since the onset of industrial fishing.*
- **Conversion:**
 - *More land was converted to cropland in the 30 years after 1950 than in the 150 years between 1700 and 1850, and now approximately one quarter (24%) of Earth's terrestrial surface has been transformed to cultivated systems.*
- **The diversity of life:**
 - *Humans are currently responsible for the sixth major extinction event in the history of the Earth, and the greatest since the dinosaurs disappeared, 65 million years ago.*
- **Degradation:**
 - *Since about 1980, approximately 35% of mangroves have been lost, while 20% of the world's coral reefs have been destroyed and a further 20% badly degraded or destroyed*

Over two decades after these after these observations, the situation has worsened rather than improve.

Living Beyond Our Means (2005) comes up with the following predictions:

- *Everyone in the world depends on nature and ecosystem services to provide the conditions for a decent, healthy, and secure life.*
- *Humans have made unprecedented changes to ecosystems in recent decades to meet growing demands for food, fresh water, fiber, and energy.*
- *These changes have helped to improve the lives of billions, but at the same time they weakened nature's ability to deliver other key services such as purification of air and water, protection from disasters, and the provision of medicines.*
- *Among the outstanding problems identified by this assessment are the dire state of many of the world's fish stocks; the intense vulnerability of the 2 billion people living in dry regions to the loss of ecosystem services, including water supply; and the growing threat to ecosystems from climate change and nutrient pollution.*
- *Human activities have taken the planet to the edge of a massive wave of species extinctions, further threatening our own well-being.*
- *The loss of services derived from ecosystems is a significant barrier to the achievement of the Millennium Development Goals to reduce poverty, hunger, and disease.*
- *The pressures on ecosystems will increase globally in coming decades unless human attitudes and actions change.*
- *Measures to conserve natural resources are more likely to succeed if local communities are given ownership of them, share the benefits, and are involved in decisions.*
- *Even today's technology and knowledge can reduce considerably the human impact on ecosystems. They are unlikely to be deployed fully, however, until ecosystem services cease to be perceived as free and limitless, and their full value is taken into account.*
- *Better protection of natural assets will require coordinated efforts across all sections of governments, businesses, and international institutions. The productivity of ecosystems depends on policy choices on investment, trade, subsidy, taxation, and regulation, among others.*

Overcoming Barriers to Development (Human Development Report (2009)) concludes that:

The world is witnessing unprecedented losses and changes in biodiversity and ecosystem services, which are having a negative effect on human well-being and sustainable development.

Given the situation, the Report observes that the future development of all countries will be impaired if these losses are not reversed, but especially hard hit will be developing countries in their efforts to alleviate poverty. Public and private stakeholders therefore need to mitigate and adapt to changes in biodiversity and ecosystem services through appropriate policy decisions. Such efforts are, however, knowledge-intensive and need to be supported by a dynamic science-policy platform that is credible, salient and legitimate, recommends the Report.

We have so far discoursed on the broader picture of the sad state of our environment and the ensuing effects on humanity (society), not as a result of natural wear and tear, but as a result of our own folly. It is therefore time for action.

Getting our Acts Together – Moving from Dialogue to Action.

What are then the **Corrective** and **Mitigative** measures? Two observations and suggestions that are worth mentioning include:

Stanners Recommendations (2007)

- **Intergenerational equity**—*providing future generations with the same environmental potential as presently exist.s*
- **Decoupling economic growth from environmental degradation**—*managing economic growth to be less resource intensive and less polluting.*

- **Integration of all pillars**—*integrating environmental, social and economic sectors when developing sustainability policies.*
- **Ensuring environmental adaptability and resilience** *maintaining and enhancing the adaptive capacity of the environmental system.*
- **Preventing irreversible long-term damage to ecosystems and human health**
- **Ensuring distributional equity**—*avoiding unfair or high environmental costs on vulnerable population.s*
- **Accepting global responsibility** — *assuming responsibility for environmental effects that occur outside areas of jurisdiction*
- **Education and grassroots involvement**—*people and communities investigating problems and developing new solutions.*

Living Beyond our Means Final Recommendations (2005) examines the following:

Institutions and governance

- *Include ecosystem protection in all decision-making.*
- *Improve coordination among multilateral environmental agreements and other international institutions.*
- *Make government and the private sector more transparent and accountable.*
- *Get the scale right.*
- *Protect the whole ecosystem, not just its parts.*

Economics and incentives

- *Eliminate subsidies for unsustainable resource use.*
- *Harness the power of markets.*

Social and behavioral changes

- *Reduce consumption of unsustainably managed ecosystem services.*
- *Emphasis on communication and education.*
- *Empower the disempowered.*

Technological responses

- *Promote technologies that increase crop yields without increasing pollution and land degradation.*
- *Restore degraded ecosystems.*
- *Promote technologies to increase energy efficiency and reduce greenhouse gas emissions.*

We now appear to know what we are faced with, what our responsibilities are, and undoubtedly what we need to do to reverse situations that we actually created, or helped to create, directly or indirectly, knowingly or unknowingly, or out of ignorance, or misinformation, or lies:

The idea of infinite or unlimited growth, which proves so attractive to economists, financiers and experts in technology . . . is based on the lie that there is an infinite supply of the earth's goods, and this leads to the planet being squeezed dry beyond every limit.

Pope Francis, Laudato si (2015).

We need to accept that we human beings have made choices that have led to the destruction of forests and wildlife habitats, the contamination of water resources, the pollution of the atmosphere through the use of fossil fuels, and our unsustainable lifestyles based on overconsumption and overproduction of waste, in other words, all the elements responsible for the destruction of our planet.

Businesses, especially large corporations and multinational corporations (MNCs) have been time and again accused of putting Profit before People and Planet. Corporations are major entities in the world and thus have an enormous impact (negative and positive) on all our lives. To most corporations, making a profit is goal number one – but some of those companies take it way too far, sacrificing the health and safety of the planet and its inhabitants for bigger financial reserves. Far too many corporations turn a blind eye to the consequences of their destructive, exploitative practices. The worst of them are engaged in activities that should be considered as criminal, and the list of such illegal and criminal activities is rather long. Several measures have been put in place to regulate corporations and render them transparent, but current voluntary approaches, such as **CSR- Corporate Social Responsibility**, has proved to be inadequate. Politicians and policy makers also appear to be failing as countless measures pushed and lobbied for favours corporations directly or indirectly, enabling them to get out of some of their responsibilities on environmental and human issues.

So much said and yet so little done, not because of lack of goodwill, but rather as a result of opposition or reluctance from those only concerned with profit. Since it is not so easy to fight against the dark side of Capitalism, there need to be result-oriented interventions that can only be accomplished through specific management strategies involving policies, legislations, measurement and auditing tools, assessment, monitoring and certification, to mention a few. The time of rhetorics and great promises is long gone. And let us have the courage to plead guilty to our indifference, as charged:

In an age when man has forgotten his origins and is blind even to his most essential needs for survival, water along with other resources has become the victim of his indifference.

Rachel Carson (1962)

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